

HISTORICAL AND PILGRIMAGE SITES IN THE TERRITORY OF
UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article highlights the significance of historical and pilgrimage sites in the territory of Uzbekistan, their role as cultural heritage, and the issues related to the study and preservation of these sites in the life of the people. The article analyzes famous pilgrimage sites and historical monuments located in various regions of Uzbekistan and their cultural and spiritual importance. Additionally, the potential of these sites for tourism and travel has been examined.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, historical monuments, pilgrimage sites, cultural heritage, spiritual significance, preservation, tourism, traditions, national values, archaeology, cultural heritage protection.

Introduction. Uzbekistan is considered one of the countries rich in historical and cultural heritage. Many pilgrimage sites, mosques, mausoleums, and other historical monuments associated with centuries-old history and rich culture are preserved here. Pilgrimage sites are not only of religious and spiritual importance but also serve as significant social and cultural centers in the lives of the people. Since ancient times, such places have played an important role in preserving the unity, customs, and traditions of the people. Therefore, the processes of studying and protecting them are also of urgent importance.

At the end of the 20th century, major historical changes on a global scale not only altered the world political map but also provided many nations with the

opportunity to restore their valuable traditions and create new prospects for themselves. One of the most important historical significances of Uzbekistan's independence is that it created opportunities to restore religious values and sacred pilgrimage sites that are holy to us. Uzbekistan is a country rich in numerous pilgrimage sites and sacred places. Blessed corners, historical and religious pilgrimage sites are present in all regions of our sacred homeland [1, p. 56].

Historically, the peoples who lived in this land, once called Mawarannahr and Turkestan, have carefully preserved many pilgrimage sites and sacred places over the centuries and passed them down as a legacy to future generations.

Great scholars who have made a significant contribution to the development of world science lived in the Central Asian region. These scholars also contributed greatly to Islamic culture and the teachings of Sufism. The vast spiritual heritage left by them is of great historical importance not only in their own time but also today.

Many revered saints who made significant contributions to Islam, religious values, and Islamic religious development glorified virtues essential for humanity through their activities and spiritual legacies.

The vital and pressing issues related to the morality and enlightenment of spirituality - honesty and purity, faith and belief, diligence and patriotism, kindness and generosity, broad-mindedness, and compassion - which define a nation and people, have not been overlooked in the works of these great historical figures who contributed to the development of Islam.

After gaining its independence, our people's attitude towards the country's past, rich historical heritage, spiritual values, and traditions has fundamentally changed.

There are also a number of pilgrimage sites in Tashkent city and Tashkent region. The Hazrati Imam complex, located in the Sebzor mahalla of Tashkent city, is rightfully considered one of the main monumental complexes in the city. The name of this pilgrimage site comes from Abu Bakr Muhammad Kaffal Shoshi, one

of the first imams of the Muslim world born in Tashkent, who was known as a scholar of religious knowledge. This well-known figure in the Islamic world passed away in 366 AH and was buried outside the city walls along the Kaykovus canal in a well-maintained area, around which a cemetery later appeared [2, p. 108].

According to some sources, the mausoleum built over his grave existed as early as the 13th century but was later destroyed. In the 16th century, a new mausoleum was constructed on its foundation. The inscription on the mausoleum's door bears the names of architect Ghulam Husayn and calligrapher scribe Qudrat, as well as the construction date 948 AH (1541 AD). The mausoleum and the adjacent areas have been a major pilgrimage site, and the complex that later appeared there took its name from it. According to specialists, this pilgrimage site belongs to one of the rare types of mausoleums typical for Sufi centers and holds great historical significance [2, p. 110].

Inside the mausoleum, there is a wooden sarcophagus (saghana), which is believed to have been placed over the grave of Abu Bakr Muhammad Kaffal Shoshi. There are also four other wooden sarcophagi inside. Outside, on both sides of the main portal, there are additional sarcophagi. At the entrance, there is a two-tiered carved door. The upper part of the door bears inscriptions that have become almost unreadable [2, p. 110].

In Tashkent city, considered the political and cultural center of Uzbekistan, special attention has been given to the repair and restoration of the buildings in the Hazrati Imam (Hastimom) pilgrimage complex. By 2007, significant works were carried out at the Hazrati Imam complex alongside other sacred sites in the country. On February 20, 2007, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, issued a special decree "On Supporting the Hazrati Imam Public Fund." Thanks to the initiatives of the President, the pilgrimage site, which had been revered by people for centuries, was restored to its original state.

One of the pilgrimage sites restored during the years of independence is the Zangiota complex. This pilgrimage site is associated with the name of Zangi Ota Oikhodja ibn Tokhirkhoja, one of the prominent representatives of the Yasavi Sufi order, who lived about 800 years ago [3, p. 91].

Zangi Ota is renowned for his knowledge, diligence, humanity, wisdom, and honesty, and he was one of the great figures who made a significant contribution to the development of his era [4, p. 7]. The Zangiota complex and pilgrimage site is an architectural monument located in the village of Zangiota in Tashkent region. It was initially constructed in the 15th century on the initiative of Amir Timur and later completed by Mirzo Ulugbek. The Zangiota pilgrimage complex includes the mausoleums of Zangi Ota and Anbar Bibi. The complex consists of a mausoleum, a gateway, a madrasa, a mosque, a khanqah (Sufi lodge), a minaret, and a pool. The mausoleum of Anbar Bibi, the pool, the khanqah, and the gateway were built separately. The Zangiota mausoleum is adjacent to the madrasa and mosque, with entrances to the courtyard through gates.

Initially, the Zangi Ota mausoleum was a simple, undecorated four-room structure. Its white marble tombstones are decorated with carved patterns and Arabic inscriptions. Later, a portal with tile decorations was added in front of the mausoleum. The construction of the mausoleum began in the 1380s under Amir Timur and was completed in the early 15th century during the reign of Ulugbek [5, p. 666].

The Zangiota complex, located in the village of Zangiota in the Tashkent region, comprises the mausoleums of Zangiota and Anbar Bibi, a gateway, madrasa, mosque, khanqah (Sufi lodge), minaret, and pool. The Anbar Bibi mausoleum, pool, khanqah, and gateway are separate structures. The Zangiota mausoleum stands next to the madrasa and mosque, with courtyard access through gates on the northeast and northwest sides. The minaret is built closer to the mosque and mausoleum, near the middle of the courtyard.

The complex is approached via an avenue lined with poplar trees, and an ancient cemetery adjoins the complex from the south, surrounded by a wall. The portal of the Zangiota mausoleum faces the courtyard, while the other three sides adjoin the cemetery.

Originally, the Zangiota mausoleum was a four-room structure (including a pilgrimage room, tomb chamber, and two small adjacent rooms) without decoration. The interior walls of the rooms were built on an arcade base, with eight-sided corner supports and domes of various shapes. There are niches and brackets carved into the walls. The white marble tombstone in the tomb chamber bears delicate carvings and Arabic inscriptions. Later, a portal was constructed in front of the mausoleum and decorated with tilework. The exterior walls of the portal and rooms, as well as the pilgrimage room and tomb chamber's base, are adorned with polished bricks and multicolored carved tiles. The interior walls are covered with plaster, with the mihrab decorated with tilework shaped like the letter "P" and Arabic calligraphy. The dome decorations are gilded. The portal's prominent borders are decorated with terracotta, glazed bricks, and mosaic tiles, with eight-cornered turunj (ornamental knobs).

It has been established that the mausoleum was built by Amir Timur and that the decoration work was completed during Ulugbek's reign. The portal and domes were repaired in the 16th–17th centuries. A single-story madrasa and a mosque for prayer were built next to the mausoleum. The madrasa consists of a row of cells, two gateways, and three larger rooms. It was decorated by the Kokand master Khoja Muhammad. The complex's surroundings have been beautified and it is under state protection as a historical monument.

Today, the Zangiota site is recognized as a place that provides spiritual nourishment for people [6, p. 231].

Another beautiful place is the Nurata spring. According to legends, initially, no one lived there - it was a desert surrounded by mountains on all four sides. Caravans of traders used to pass through this area. One day, an old man from a

caravan got lost and was left behind. Unable to endure the scorching heat of the desert, he wandered aimlessly in search of water. Eventually, he reached a high ridge. Climbing to the top, he saw a green plant. At first, the old man was amazed to see such greenery thriving in the scorching heat. As he descended closer to the grass, he began to feel moisture. Then he dug the soil around the grass a little with his hands and found mud. Without even noticing his fatigue, he continued digging. Suddenly, water started to gush out from a deep place. After that, the old man settled there. Gradually, the trees he planted grew, and the area turned into a green oasis. Passing caravans stopped by the old man's spring, resting there for a day or two. The old man's name was Nur. Because he created such a wonderful place in the harsh desert, people respectfully called it Nurata. The place where the water appeared was named "Nurata spring." Over time, people started settling here, and the area took the name Nurata, after the spring.

Ancient Nur is one of the historical cities of the Nur-Turon land. It was an important point on the Great Silk Road connecting East and West. Visitors enjoy its beautiful spring, ancient water infrastructure - underground canals (karez), Nur fortress, Katta Gumbaz (Great Dome), and the "Chil Ustun" (Forty Columns) mausoleum. These pilgrimage sites are considered an important source for fostering the culture of religious tolerance among our youth [7, pp. 58-65].

The city's history is richly described in historical books and chronicles. It is specially mentioned in the rare 10th-century work "History of Bukhara." Its author, historian and nobleman Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ja'far an-Narshahi, provides the following description: "Nur is a large place. It has a Friday mosque and many ribats (caravanserais). People from Bukhara and other places come there every year for pilgrimage. The people of Bukhara exaggerate about this event, saying: 'A person who visits Nur attains the virtue of one who has performed Hajj; when returning from this pilgrimage, they decorate the city with blessed objects brought from there.' For this reason, Nur is also called 'Nuri Bukhara' in other provinces."

Nur means light, brightness, or radiance.

Nurata – Etymology and Historical Significance. Nurata means:

- a) light, brightness came into existence;
- b) light, brightness was bestowed or gifted.

Nurata is named after this mountain. In this context, “Ota” (father) in Nurata carries a divine meaning, referring to a sacred pilgrimage site. The terms “Nur” and “Nurata” have been used for many years, while the name “Nurata” started to be mentioned only from the 20th century onward.

There are many folk legends and stories about the spring and the city’s name. For the local people, the spring is regarded as a miraculous place and highly revered.

Indeed, the spring is considered a wondrous gift from God. For this reason, numerous beautiful legends and tales have been created to describe the unparalleled mercy and kindness of Allah.

Legend: Long ago, caravans used to pass through this place. One caravan stopped and spent the night in the mountains. When they woke up at dawn, a miraculous event occurred: a bright light appeared between them and mist rose. Those who had never witnessed such a sight before were filled with awe and fear. Upon investigation, they found a large spring sparkling in a hollow at the foot of the mountain, with mist rising from its basin. The spring was so clear that travelers, who had wandered the world, said they had never seen such clean, delicious, and sweet water in their lives.

People rejoiced, saying, “God has granted us light (Nur).” Since then, the place has been called Nurata.

Another legend tells a similar story: the amazed Alexander the Great (Iskandar Zulqarnayn) ordered the spring to be cleaned from reeds and bushes and developed it.

These legends and the deeper meaning of the sources represent “water of life” (obi hayot). Indeed, in the names Nur, Nurata, and Nurata, the spring water shines like light.

The ancient Nur spring has served for centuries as a source of life and spirituality for people. It grants life and light to all living things in this blessed land.

The spring is located at an altitude of 530 meters above sea level on the western side of the Aktau mountain range. Its water is pure, transparent, colorless, odorless, and healing: one liter contains more than fifteen microelements including chlorine, sulfate, potassium, magnesium, calcium, silicon, carbonate, sodium, gold, and silver ions. The temperature is astonishingly stable at +19.5°C year-round. The spring produces 250–270 liters of water per moment, though this volume fluctuates seasonally.

The scenery of the spring is extremely elegant. In the clear water, stones and sands appear like pearl beads in various shapes. Fish swim and play in it. One can truly acknowledge the praise given to it from west to east.

Over different periods, people have constructed various structures around the spring. The spring mainly consists of two large water sources: one circular, the other rectangular. On the west side, the circular spring is called “Nurgulato.” It is considered the main spring, providing nearly half of the total water volume of the whole spring. The water flows under a bridge directly into the rectangular spring below.

Almost all around the spring and beneath it, clear water seeps and bubbles out from beautiful and variously shaped stone cavities. On the southern side, water flows from stone cavities shaped like a “five-clawed hand” in an amazing spectacle, with a generous water volume.

In this condition, the rectangular spring often overflows, and its clear, pure water flows northwards toward the city through a large canal.

It is clear that since ancient times, the people of Nurata have given great importance to the effective use of this unique spring and underground water. The ancestors of Nurata were skilled and wise in using ancient irrigation methods properly, efficiently, and - most importantly - fairly.

As noted above, there is clear evidence supporting this fact.

Over the years, remarkable structures were built around the spring. The area transformed into a fortress and stronghold. The ark and its sturdy walls were restored. Among the rare monuments of the Nurata spring are the Sahabas' khanaqah (spiritual retreat), the Great Dome Mosque, the Friday Mosque called Chilustun, the madrasa, and the Abu Hasan Nuri tomb. These were constructed thanks to the high level of craftsmanship of our ancestors, and each has its unique architectural style and history.

Conclusion. Historical and pilgrimage sites in Uzbekistan serve as important links between the past and the present. Their preservation and development are crucial not only for protecting cultural heritage but also for safeguarding national identity and promoting tourism. Each pilgrimage site or historical monument, with its uniqueness and significance, offers an opportunity to get closer to the rich cultural history and spiritual worldview of our people. Therefore, protecting such places, raising public awareness about them, and conducting scientific research are essential tasks.

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